

Thiazolidone Derivatives

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Several thiazolidone derivatives have been prepared either by the cycloaddition of thioglycollic acid with different Schiff bases or by direct condensation of aryl or thiazoleamine, aldehyde and thioglycollic acid. Their arylidene derivatives have been prepared by condensation with different aldehydes. Structure elucidation of the thiazolidones has been made on the basis of their elemental analysis, IR and mass spectra. The principal fragmentations in the mass spectra have been discussed. The fungicidal screening data of the compounds are also presented.

THIAZOLIDONE derivatives are well known biologically active compounds¹⁻⁶. Surrey⁷ and Long⁸ prepared several substituted thiazolidones and found them possessing anaesthetic, anticonvulsant and sedative properties. Besides, compounds having N-C-S grouping have wide range of biological activities such as antitubercular⁹, antiradiation¹⁰, nematocidal¹¹ and antifungal¹². In view of the varied physiological activities of thiazolidone derivatives, it was considered of interest to prepare some thiazolidone derivatives for a study of their fungicidal and other related properties. The thiazolidones are prepared (i) by the cycloaddition of thioglycollic acid with different Schiff bases (ii) by direct condensation of aryl or thiazoleamine, aldehyde and thioglycollic acid.

We had reported earlier¹³ that, Schiff bases derived from 4-aryl-2-aminothiazoles and 2-amino-benzothiazoles possess considerable fungicidal activity. The present investigation was undertaken to compare the effect of azomethine linkage and thiazolidone ring on fungicidal activity. The thiazolidones are prepared from Schiff bases derived from ethylenediamine, *p*-phenylenediamine and 4-aryl-2-aminothiazoles. The thiazolidones are also condensed with different aldehydes in presence of fused sodium acetate and glacial acetic acid to give arylidene derivatives.

Experimental

Preparation of thiazolidone compound :

Method (i) : A mixture of appropriate Schiff base (0.01 mole) and thioglycollic acid (0.015 mole) in 30 ml of dry benzene is refluxed for 3½-4 hr. Excess of solvent and thioglycollic acid is removed under vacuum. The residue is washed thoroughly first with NaHCO₃ solution and then with water, dried and crystallised from either, ethanol or acetone.

Method (ii) : A mixture of appropriate amine (0.01 mole) and aryl aldehyde in 30 ml of dry benzene is refluxed in Dean and Stark apparatus. After

separation of considerable amount of water, thioglycollic acid (0.015 mole) is added to it and refluxing continued till no more water collects. Excess of thioglycollic acid and the solvent is removed under vacuum and the residue is worked out as above ; yield 50-70%. The compounds from (i) and (ii) are found to be the same from m.p., m.m.p., analytical data and spectral analysis. The m.p., analytical data and fungicidal data of various thiazolidones have been reported in Tables 1 and 2.

Preparation of arylidene thiazolidones : A mixture of an appropriate aldehyde (0.01 mole), thiazolidone (0.01 mole) and fused sodium acetate (1 g) in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) is refluxed for 6 hr till clear solution is obtained. The excess solvent is distilled off and the residue is washed thoroughly with cold water, dried and crystallised from alcohol or acetic acid ; yield 30-40%. The melting points, analytical data and fungicidal data have been recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	m.p. °C	% inhibition at 500 ppm
1.	2-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	-(CH ₂) ₂ -	180	22.7
2.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	"	>240	37.8
3.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	"	184	19.2
4.	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	"	160	10.7
5.	2-OH-naphthyl	"	235(d)	78.9
6.	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	-C ₆ H ₄ -	206	34.5
7.	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	"	>250	26.7
8.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	"	230	29.4
9.	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	"	135(d)	35.8
10.	2-OH-naphthyl	"	>250	82.0

d : decomposes
All compounds gave consistent sulphur and nitrogen analysis.

TABLE 2

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	m.p. °C	%inhibition at 500 ppm
1.	4-OC ₂ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	205	15.9
2.	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	"	251	28.6
3.	4-OH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	5-Br-2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	177	11.0
4.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	"	95	22.0
5.	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	"	>240	27.0
6.	β-naphthyl	"	205	12.8
7.	H	3,5-Br ₂ -2-OH-C ₆ H ₃	167	11.8
8.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	"	188	5.5
9.	C ₆ H ₅	2-OH-naphthyl	125	100.0
10.	4-OH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	"	160	89.5
11.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	"	110	99.8
12.	C ₆ H ₅	4-N(OH) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	137	19.1
13.	4-OH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	"	193	10.8
14.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	"	172	3.0
15.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	4-OH-C ₆ H ₄	207	11.0
16.	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	165	5.2
17.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	"	105	9.2
18.	C ₆ H ₅	p-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	147	24.5
19.	4-OH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	"	176	7.5
20.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	"	172	10.0
21.	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	190	12.5
22.	C ₆ H ₅	"	167	4.0

All compounds gave consistent sulphur and nitrogen analysis.

TABLE 3

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	m.p. °C	%inhibition at 500 ppm
1.	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	4-N(OH) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	212	78.6
2.	C ₆ H ₅	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	167	73.2
3.	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	230	74.5
4.	C ₆ H ₅	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	150	67.9
5.	C ₆ H ₅	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	148	70.2
6.	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	128(d)	74.0
7.	C ₆ H ₅	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	76	79.1
8.	C ₆ H ₅	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	4-OH-C ₆ H ₄	220(d)	69.0
9.	β-naphthyl	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	121	87.9

d : decompose.

All the compounds gave consistent sulphur and nitrogen analysis.

Results and Discussion

The structure of the thiazolidones was elucidated on the basis of ir and mass spectra. Schiff bases generally give a strong sharp band in between 1630-1615 cm⁻¹ (C=N stretch). The band due to C=N stretching is lost on thiazolidone formation

and a strong tertiary amide stretch (>N-C=O) is observed around 1680 cm⁻¹. In arylidene thiazolidones, the carbonyl group absorption occurs in

between 1650-1660 cm⁻¹ due to conjugation of carbonyl group with aliphatic double bond and an aromatic ring^{1,4}.

The mass spectra fragmentation pattern of four representative thiazolidones I-IV are in good agreement with their suggested structures. The thiazolidones I and II both are rather stable and show prominent molecular ion peaks (base peak) whereas moderate intensity of molecular ion peaks (32 and 42% of the base peak) are observed in III and IV. A peak at M-42 in both I and II results from the loss of -CH₂-CO from the molecular ion. Nearly all the abundant ions in the spectra of I and II result by cleavage of 1, 2 and 3, 4 bonds of the thiazolidone ring. This can occur with or without hydrogen transfer (V) and results in a cluster of peaks near m/e 299, 298 and 297 in the spectrum of I and near m/e 333, 332 and 331 in the spectrum of II. The most abundant ions for I and II are at m/e 299 and 333 respectively (V+H).

I: R = H, R₁ = Cl
II: R = R, R₁ = Cl

III: R = Cl

IV R = Cl

V

Structure I-V

Peaks due to further fragmentation of V dominate both spectra and the fragmentation pattern is similar to that of Schiff bases reported earlier^{1,3}. In the spectrum of III a peak of low intensity at M-42 and another at M-74 are observed as in the case of I and II. All the other prominent ions in the spectrum of III result from two important modes of decomposition of the molecular ion. One fragmentation results from the straight forward homolytic cleavage of the central C-C bond. This gives ion at m/e 226. The second major fragmentation involves cleavage at one of the C-N bonds of the original ethylenediamine portion, which can also occur with or without hydrogen transfer. Their formation is depicted below (Scheme 1). The cleavage could as well result in charge residing on other fragment to give ions at m/e 240, 239 and 238.

Similar fragmentations also result from M-74 ion, giving ions at m/e 166, 152 and 138. The ion at m/e 152 by loss of HCN gives a strong peak at m/e 125 which may be pictured as a chlorotropylium ion. In the spectrum of IV, low peaks due to molecular ion, M-74 and M-148 are observed. Two other peaks which are of importance in IV are one at m/e 335 which results by loss of two HCN molecules and ClC_6H_4 radical from the molecular ion and another at m/e 136 ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_8\text{NCl}^+$) which is the base peak in the spectrum.

Fungicidal assay: Poisoned food technique¹⁵ is used for fungicidal assay. All compounds are tested for toxicity towards *Curvularia* species isolated from diseased rice leaves infected with *Helminthosporium oryzae*. Results at 500 ppm have been calculated using the equation:

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = \left(1 - \frac{X}{Y}\right) \times 100$$

where X=growth with drug and Y=growth in control.

Not much structure activity relationship could be drawn from the fungicidal data since the compounds (except a few) are not very much toxic towards the *Curvularia* species. Only the compounds containing hydroxynaphthyl group at 3-position of the thiazolidone ring showed some activity. Arylidene thiazolidones are found to be more active than thiazolidones.

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